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Capturing the essence of success through the life stories of empowered Indian women

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This is a concise effort to depict gender socialization of women folk. This work is an unbiased understanding of underlying characteristics of empowerment, scientifically gathered and without any feminist nuances. Social status of women has had its crests and falls all along Indian history. The focus of this study is on the analysis of the environment, socialization, and decision making processes of seven iconic personalities in the Indian national scenario. These individuals have been selected on the basis of empowering behavior exhibited by them. They are: Kiran Bedi, Bachendri Pal, Indira Gandhi, Ela R. Bhatt, Sonal Mansingh, Sai Paranjpye, and Kalpana Lajmi. Although they all came from different socio-economic backgrounds they had a striking similarity in forming their ideologies as per their aspirations and asserting their independent nature irrespective of varied circumstances. Their focus was clear and line of action concrete. The success they acquired can partially be attributed to their internal locus of control. With their power of communication, personal involvement, problem solving particularity at work, systematic working, transparency, personal accountability, constant internal audit, social audit of performance and review, they were able to cross the hurdles of life and reach their goals. It is found here that family support is required only until a certain stage of development after which the individual needs to be self-reliant. However a support from organizational set up can also act as a facilitator. Not only were their families supportive, but also their irrepressible spirit turned all stumbling blocks into stepping stones. They had aspirations and developed mastery by their work experience and competence. They were daring and were able to establish their own norms.

Keywords: life stories, women empowerment

Throughout the history of mankind, the notion of success has been defined differentially for men and women. And as a consequence even the milestones for success got differentiated through socialization, for both the sexes. However, the major problem comes when we see that the success story of males got highlighted and women had to play not only a secondary and devaluated role, but slowly started ignoring the success of women throughout almost all the corners of this world. This research work was undertaken to identify those domains where women reached a level which could not be sidelined. And we started this journey by analyzing the life stories of seven successful women who attained a status which has been a pride for the nation.

The ability of women to carry on their duties effectively and efficiently for social benefit amounts to success. Success here is metaphorical in nature and not to be benchmarked against performance by successful men. The criterion of success can be made transparent by analyzing the processes that made successful ones grow to such heights that they reach to iconic status. Understanding the process by which they imbibe, rectify and develop themselves form a not so noticeable state to a state of full realization can be termed as empowerment. The relation between the terms "success" and "empowerment" is mutually conjunctive. Success gives rise to empowerment and empowerment denotes success. This mutual process, when deployed by those who are struggling to achieve may enhance the possibility of reaching the peak in their lives and careers.

Success can be a very broad concept; meaning different things to

different people. However, it has an inherent tendency to attract and bind each one connected to social and the material world. An attempt is made here to provide an operational definition of the term. The word success generates spur, fervor, enthusiasm, happiness and joy..., in as many ways as we experience it. In the present study, the focus is on success as defined, determined and practiced by women whose life journeys are analyzed and deliberated. Real success however, means to have the power to create at will what you need the power to acquire those things that are truly necessary for your absolute existence and happiness.

How can I become empowered? You can start by never being a victim. A strong, independent woman who is happy and successful is less likely to succumb to catastrophic events and domestic violence than an unhappy woman is with low self-esteem. Many times the only thing separating a woman from success is her own self, or rather, her level of self-worth.

Unfortunately, many women still succumb to accepting her own worth as decided by others, or take themselves as less than men even in the new millennium especially in the Asian countries.

At the core of empowerment is the principle that each person is considered in the light of his/her unique capabilities and circumstances. Thus, empowerment cannot be a set of monolithic principles applied regardless of the situation. It must be tailored to the needs and abilities of each individual. To push someone beyond his or her wishes or capabilities is probably the most disempowering and undermining treatment that can be inflicted.

Empowerment and its relation to success

Having explored the concepts of success and empowerment, we now will try to explain the relationship between the two terms. As mentioned earlier, Derr (1986) defines 'career success' as 'both being